

Beyond incentives: psychological need satisfaction, non-financial motivation, and managerial effectiveness in public organizations

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Abstract

Public-sector organisations operate in contexts where financial incentives remain limited and organisational change unfolds slowly, making employee motivation depend increasingly on how work is experienced in everyday managerial practice. This article examines how psychological need satisfaction (NS) shapes employees' evaluations of non-financial motivational methods (NFMMS) and managerial effectiveness in highly institutionalised public-sector settings. Drawing on Self-Determination Theory and complementary need-based perspectives, the study conceptualises NS as a multidimensional construct comprising basic, relational and higher-order needs that reflect key features of public-sector work, including procedural security, interpersonal climate and opportunities for development. Using survey data from 807 employees in Romanian public organisations and Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM), the analysis tests direct and mediated relationships linking the three need domains, overall NS and two evaluative outcomes: perceived NFMMS effectiveness and perceived managerial effectiveness. The findings show that higher-order needs related to autonomy, recognition and development opportunities exert the strongest influence on NS. In turn, NS operates as an interpretive mechanism through which employees make sense of both practice-level motivational signals and supervisory behaviour. Evaluations of NFMMS and managerial effectiveness depend less on formal HRM instruments and more on how managerial conduct unfolds in daily interactions. The article offers a context-sensitive refinement of established need-based frameworks by showing how motivational meaning develops in public organisations characterised by constrained discretion, procedural control and limited incentive flexibility. It contributes to employee relations and human-centred HRM research by clarifying how psychological need satisfaction and managerial behaviour jointly shape motivational evaluations in institutionalised environments.

Highlights

- Psychological need satisfaction strongly predicts employees' evaluations of both non-financial motivational methods and managerial practices, underlining its central role in how public employees interpret motivational signals.
- Higher-order needs – growth, creativity, recognition and opportunities for meaningful contribution – exert the strongest influence within the need structure, making them especially salient for motivational evaluations.
- Motivation depends less on formal HRM instruments and more on employees' lived experience of work, particularly their interpretations of fairness, procedural clarity and relational support.
- Human-centred HRM practices, especially credible recognition and participatory behaviours, can enhance engagement even in public organisations operating under procedural constraints and limited resources.

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